

Literature Review on Exhaust Emission and Assessment of Air Quality

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Abstract

Environmental toxicology explores how different physical, chemical, and biological factors adversely impact living organisms in ecosystems, including humans. Data show that exhaust emissions significantly contribute to environmental toxicity, making them a key focus of worldwide research efforts. This paper focuses on modeling exhaust emissions and underscores the contributions of various researchers in this field. It concludes by pinpointing current research gaps and detailing the goals of the proposed study.

Keywords: Exhaust emissions; modeling; artificial neural network (ANN); environmental toxicity.

1. Introduction

According to Ke et al. (2022), environmental health encompasses factors related to human well-being and quality of life, which are influenced by psychosocial, physical, biological, and social elements of the environment. It involves the practice and theory of preventing, assessing, and mitigating harmful environmental conditions that could impact the health of current and future generations. Over recent decades, rapid industrial and technological advancements, coupled with the unsustainable use of non-renewable resources, have led to an increase in environmental toxic agents. These agents contribute to various diseases, with heightened risks for children, pregnant women, the elderly, and patients with preexisting conditions. The impact of air pollution on human health, leading to higher morbidity and mortality rates, has intensified the focus of toxicological studies on industrial air pollution and its effects on the general population. Asha et al. (2022) further adds that, on using technological and economic growth of cities, environmental pollution is increasing like air, water and noise pollution. Mainly, air pollution consists of direct effect on human health by the disclosure of particulates and pollutants that has improved the attention in air pollution and its influences amongst the research field. Solid and liquid particles,

and certain hydrocarbons suspended in air, contribute to pollution. Such particles and vapors can be released into the atmosphere by automobiles, industries, sand, particles, toxins and mildew, rock formations, and forest fires. Air pollutants are solid and liquid stopped in our environment. High levels of air pollution could have a quantity of negative health effects. It tends to raise the chances of getting respiratory disease, cardiovascular disease, and lung cancer. Short - range and long visibility to air pollutants has indeed been connected to negative health impacts. The primary causes of air pollution include agriculture, burning of fossil fuels, residential heating, natural disaster, exhaust from industries and factories.

According to Liu et al. (2022), urban air quality has been regarded as a crucial issue for decades due to the rising concerns for human health. Exposure to poor-quality air may cause allergic reactions and even lead to respiratory and circulatory diseases. These diseases can contribute to enormous economic loss due to the demand for medical treatments and the decline in productivity. Mahendra et al. (2023) highlight that air quality has become a major concern due to its direct impact on human health. Mishra and Gupta (2024) further noted that with rising urbanization and industrialization in developing countries, air pollution has emerged as a significant threat to human well-being. Environmental toxicology focuses on the behavior and effects of toxic substances within biological systems, environmental structures, and food chains. While this field examines the negative impacts of chemical, biological, and physical hazards on ecosystems, its emphasis on human health makes it crucial in addressing public health issues (Asha et al., 2022). According to Nigam et al. (2013), air pollution affects both the health and environment of living organisms.

Given these considerations, the current research is dedicated to environmental toxicity and centers on the contributions of researchers in modeling exhaust emissions through artificial emissions. It concludes by examining the identified research gaps and outlining the objectives of the proposed study.

2. Literature Review

Present section focuses on the academic aspects of the research and presents the scenario of research in the field of exhaust emissions and assessment of air quality and contributions of researchers in the field, as presented in upcoming sub-sections.

2.1 Scenario of Research in the Field of Exhaust Emissions and Assessment of Air Quality

Figure 2.1 shows the radar graph showing the research work done in last ten years for the keywords, exhaust emissions and assessment of air quality, from www.scholar.google.com, as follows.

Figure 2.1: Radar Graph showing Research on the keywords “exhaust emissions and assessment of air quality” (www.scholar.google.com)

Proceeding in the similar manner, the following figure shows the number of citations appeared from different countries, in the last ten years, obtained from www.dimensions.ai.

Figure 2.2: Radar Graph showing the Number of Citations from Different Countries in last ten years (www.dimensions.ai)

2.2 Overview of Techniques used for Evaluation of Exhaust Emissions and Air Quality

This section synthesizes findings from recent studies, highlighting different methodologies employed in the evaluation of exhaust emissions and air quality, as follows..

One of the primary methods for measuring exhaust emissions is the use of Portable Emissions Measurement Systems (PEMS). This technique allows for real-time monitoring of emissions under actual driving conditions, providing a more accurate representation of vehicle performance compared to traditional laboratory tests. Adamiak Adamiak (2023) compares PEMS results with laboratory systems, emphasizing the necessity of real driving emissions (RDE) testing as mandated by the European Commission. Similarly, Merkisz and Pielecha Merkisz & Pielecha (2015) highlight the effectiveness of PEMS in capturing emissions during various driving cycles, underscoring its role in regulatory compliance and environmental assessments. Gallas et al. Gallas et al. (2019) also discuss the application of PEMS in real operating conditions, further supporting the importance of this method.

In addition to PEMS, other methodologies have been explored to enhance the accuracy of emission evaluations. For instance, Rymaniak Rymaniak (2023) validates a remote-sensing method for measuring emissions from two-wheelers, demonstrating the potential for innovative approaches to complement traditional methods. Furthermore, Kęska Kęska (2023) discusses the development of in vitro biological methods for assessing the toxicity of engine exhaust gases, which could provide insights into the health impacts of emissions beyond standard chemical analyses.

The integration of simulation techniques has also gained traction in emission evaluation. Yang et al. Yang et al. (2020) utilize tunable diode laser absorption spectroscopy to model diesel engine emissions, combining experimental data with simulations to improve understanding of emission characteristics. This approach aligns with findings from Xu et al. (Xu et al., 2021), who emphasize the importance of accurate emission inventories and modeling in formulating effective emission reduction strategies.

Moreover, the influence of driving behavior on emissions has been a focal point in recent studies. Andrzejewski et al. Andrzejewski et al. (2020) explore how different driving styles

impact diesel emissions, suggesting that behavioral factors must be considered in emission assessments. This is echoed by Skobiej and Pielecha (Skobiej & Pielecha, 2021), who note that the distance covered during tests significantly affects emission results, indicating that both distance and driving conditions are critical variables in emission evaluations.

The need for comprehensive assessments that consider various vehicle types and operational conditions is further supported by studies such as those by Ma et al. (2020) and Nowak et al. (2021). These studies highlight the importance of on-road measurements across different vehicle categories to capture the full spectrum of emissions, reinforcing the notion that laboratory tests alone may not adequately represent real-world scenarios.

Lastly, the ongoing development of emission reduction technologies, such as Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR), is crucial in the context of emission evaluations. Mandalia (2015) reviews EGR as an effective method for reducing NO_x emissions, illustrating the interplay between technological advancements and emission measurement methodologies.

Thus, one can analyze that evaluation of exhaust emissions has evolved significantly over the past decade, with a diverse array of techniques being employed to capture real-world conditions accurately. The integration of PEMS, remote sensing, biological assessment methods, and simulation approaches, alongside considerations of driving behavior and technological advancements, underscores the complexity and importance of this field. Future research should continue to refine these methodologies to enhance the accuracy and reliability of exhaust emission evaluations.

2.3 Contributions of Researchers in the field of Field of Exhaust Emissions and Assessment Of Air Quality

The present section presents the contributions of researchers in the investigating the applications of ANN in modeling exhaust emissions, as follows.

- **Guttikunda (2024)**

This research presents a cleaned and open-access vehicle stock database for India, along with a detailed methodology for constructing and maintaining a dynamic in-use vehicle age distribution database for future years.

- **Piccoli et al. (2024)**

The researchers suggest a three-phase adaptable modeling framework that includes a traffic model, an emission model, and an air quality model. Additionally, an optional fourth module can be incorporated to assess the impact of atmospheric pollution on the health of the local population.

- **Toro et al. (2024)**

The aim of the research paper is to evaluate how incorporating current real-world measurements of on-road NH₃ emission rates influences the simulation of NH₃ and PM_{2.5} concentrations in urban environments.

- **Dyvak et al. (2023)**

The article addresses the challenge of modeling nitrogen dioxide pollution in the atmospheric surface layer resulting from vehicle emissions. It proposes methods for interval data analysis and introduces a novel approach for developing a mathematical model to describe the distribution of nitrogen dioxide as an atmospheric pollutant, based on data with known measurement errors. This approach, presented for the first time, leads to a mathematical model in the form of a difference equation, which ensures accurate predictions of nitrogen dioxide concentrations in a specific urban area.

- **Shu et al. (2023)**

The study seeks to develop a dependable method for estimating the quantity of pollutants released by ships. Using the Ship Traffic Emission Assessment Model, the research examines the emission intensity of CO₂, NO_x, CO, NMVOC, PM_{2.5}, and SO₂ in terms of time, location, and volume. The findings indicate that ship speed has a notable impact on these emission intensities. Specifically, while the intensity of emissions in terms of time and volume is affected, the intensity of spatial emissions increases sharply when the ship's speed approaches zero.

- **Mbandi et al. (2023)**

The researchers developed a comprehensive inventory of greenhouse gases and air pollutants from road transport to examine energy emissions under various policy scenarios for Kenya's road transport sector.

- **Khreis et al. (2022)**

In this paper, the researchers reported on the performance and the linear calibration of readings from 12 commercial low-cost sensors co-located at a regulatory air quality monitoring site in Dallas, Texas, for 18 continuous measurement months. Commercial AQY1 sensors were used, and their reported readings of O₃, NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ were assessed against a regulatory monitor.

- **Barboza et al. (2022)**

According to researchers, the rising population of the world has led to an increase in energy demand which in turn contributes to environmental pollution. Clean energy for a sustainable environment is important to address climate change issues. Out of seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted by United Nations in 2015, SDGs 7 and 13 describe affordable and clean energy, and climate action, which are important for transportation and industrial sectors.

- **Macias-Hernandez et al. (2022)**

This study aims to analyze maritime traffic's effect on air quality through multiple regression analysis using recurrent neural networks (RNN), allowing one to forecast the daily concentration of PM_{2.5}.

- **Marques et al. (2022)**

According to the researchers, this work is the first to present PMF analysis of highly time-resolved PTR-ToF-MS measurements (1s resolution) of vehicle emissions.

- **Manimaran et al. (2022)**

In this research work, the experimental tests were conducted on a single-cylinder, constant speed, variable compression ratio (VCR) engine fuelled with green diesel. Initially, bio-oil was extracted from waste *Trichosanthes cucumerina* fruit seeds using the Soxhlet apparatus.

- **Ren et al. (2022)**

This work proposes artificial-intelligence-based models for calculating the exposure risk to traffic-related pollutants ($PM_{2.5}$) and choosing a low-risk commuting path to ensure healthy travel.

- **Seo et al. (2022)**

According to researchers, during the cold start and warm-up phase, modern vehicles emit considerable amounts of pollutants due to the incomplete combustion and deteriorated performance of aftertreatment devices.

- **Panchal et al. (2022)**

According to researchers, commuting by car in cities during rush hour can potentially result in the commuter being exposed to large concentrations of pollutants. The researchers investigated the differences in pollutant concentrations by commute type in real world journeys in a typical medium-sized city in the UK.

- **Xu et al. (2022)**

This study investigated clinical CKD at low air pollution levels in the Swedish Malmö Diet and Cancer Cohort in different exposure time windows.

- **Hayami et al. (2022)**

Researchers report that global limit on the sulfur content of ship fuel was reduced from 3.50% to 0.50% in January 2020 to reduce ship emissions of SO_2 and particulate matter.

- **Raghuvaran et al. (2021)**

According to researchers, production of Biodiesel is the recent technological area of research as the price of fuel increases constantly and also its eco-friendly properties

- **Jida et al. (2021)**

According to researchers, currently, vehicle-related particulate matter is the main determinant air pollution in the urban environment. This study was designed to investigate the level of fine ($PM_{2.5}$) and coarse particle (PM_{10}) concentration of roadside vehicles in Addis Ababa, the capital city of Ethiopia using artificial neural network model.

- **Hosamani et al. (2021)**

In this work, the thermal performance characteristics and emissions of VCR, one cylinder compression ignition (CI) engine fuelled with a mixture of two biodiesel in a blend with diesel has been assessed by using artificial neural network (ANN).

- **Thulasiram et al. (2021)**

According to researchers, nowadays, the emissions from the diesel engines are focused lot to minimise the environmental pollutions in accordance with the emission standards.

- **Sokhi et al. (2021)**

The researchers investigated the effects of the differences in both emissions and regional and local meteorology in 2020 compared with the period 2015–2019.

- **Tunc et al. (2021)**

According to researchers, increasing world population and rapid industrialization are growing the modern economy and causing more energy demand.

- **Salva et al. (2021)**

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the contribution of on-road mobile sources to ambient PM pollution in the selected urban area, defined as an Air Quality Management Area (AQMA) by air dispersion modeling. Researches focused on determining the extent of the impact of exhaust and non-exhaust traffic related emissions and particular vehicle categories.

- **Forsberg and Krook-Riekkola (2021)**

This study investigates the ancillary benefits on (a) APs if the transport sector is decarbonised, and (b) GHGs if APs are drastically cut and (c) the possible co-benefits from targeting APs and GHGs in parallel, using an energy-system optimisation model with a detailed and consistent representation of technology and fuel choices.

- **Jephcote et al. (2021)**

According to the researchers, the UK implemented a lockdown in Spring (2020) to curtail the person-to-person transmission of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. Measures restricted movements to one

outing per day for exercise and shopping, otherwise most people were restricted to their dwelling except for key workers (e.g. medical, supermarkets, and transport

- **KARAGÖZ (2020)**

In this study, experimental data was gathered from a single cylinder diesel engine fuelled with pyrolytic oil, neat diesel and butanol fuel blends.

- **Aydin et al. (2020)**

In the present study, the performance and emission parameters of a single cylinder diesel engine powered by biodiesel-diesel fuel blends were predicted by Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and optimized by Response Surface Methodology (RSM). The obtained results reveal that the ANN can correctly model the exhaust emission and performance parameters with the regression coefficients (R^2) between 0.8663 and 0.9858.

- **Ramprasanna et al. (2020)**

Researchers report that automobile is the chief pollutant among other sources of air pollution and it contributes more than half of the total pollution

- **Agrawal et al. (2020a)**

According to researchers, humanity is on the verge of setting new benchmarks in warming up the planet 4-5°C by triggering a series of cascading tripping points.

- **Agrawal et al. (2020b)**

Researchers report that air pollution is an important issue, especially in megacities across the world.

- **Gu et al. (2020)**

According to researchers, urban air pollution is the most serious environmental pollution problem in China.

- **Dobrzynska et al. (2020)**

According to researchers, diesel emissions have a significant impact on the atmosphere, contributing to air pollution, smog and global warming.

- **Shetty et al. (2020)**

In this paper, the researchers reported that problem with the automobile engines continues to increase in a very large scale.

- **Kolakoti (2020)**

In this endeavor, nine experiments were conducted based on Taguchi orthogonal array and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) based feedforward backpropagation was used for validation of the transesterification process.

- **Yu et al. (2020)**

This study aims to develop a hybrid approach based on back propagation artificial neural network (ANN) and spatial analysis techniques to predict particulate matter of size 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) from vehicle exhaust emissions in the State of California using aerosol optical depth (AOD) and several meteorological indicators (relative humidity, temperature, precipitation, and wind speed).

- **Catalano et al. (2020)**

This paper illustrates the early results of ongoing research developing novel methods to analyse and simulate the relationship between transport-related air pollutant concentrations and easily accessible explanatory variables. The final scope is to integrate the new models in traditional traffic management support systems for a sustainable mobility of road vehicles in urban areas.

- **Agrawal et al. (2020)**

In this study, a model using Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) has been developed to forecast pollutant concentration of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and O₃ for the current day and subsequent 4 days in a highly polluted region (32 different locations in Delhi).

- **Dutta & Jinsart (2020)**

Researchers report that Indian cities are increasingly becoming susceptible to PM₁₀ induced health effects which have become a matter of concern for the policymakers of the country. Air pollution is engulfing the comparatively smaller cities as the rapid pace of urbanization, and economic development seems not to lose steam ever.

- **Dutta & Jinsart (2020)**

The results of this research work shows that the non-linear algorithm MLP with feedforward backpropagation network topologies of ANN class, giving the best prediction value when compared with linear MLR and nonlinear CART model.

- **Wang et al. (2019)**

The main contributions of this review include: 1) Summarising the main sources and types of air pollutants as well as the emission characteristics of different sector groups; 2) Proposing the mechanism of air pollution terrain nexus; 3) Reviewing modelling and experiments approaches for air pollution terrain nexus simulation; 4) Highlighting the existing limitations and challenges. This review provides a better understanding of the air pollution terrain nexus.

- **Lyogun et al. (2019)**

The study adopted descriptive cross-sectional design with a comparative approach. Sixteen grain milling shops each were randomly selected from two major food markets in Ibadan metropolis for indoor PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} monitoring. Seventy-two respondents each were proportionately selected from grain millers and shop owners for forced expiratory volume in one second and peak expiratory flow rate tests.

- **Salvi and Salim (2019)**

According to researchers, traffic-related air pollution (TRAP) is a major contributor to global air pollution.

- **Mudway et al. (2019)**

In this paper, the researchers reported that low emission zones (LEZ) are an increasingly common, but unevaluated, intervention aimed at improving urban air quality and public health. Researchers investigated the impact of London's LEZ on air quality and children's respiratory health.

- **Font et al. (2019)**

According to the researchers, Paris and London are Europe's two megacities and both experience poor air quality with systemic breaches of the NO₂ limit value. Policy initiatives have been taken

to address this: some European-wide (e.g. Euro emission standards); others local (e.g. Low Emission Zone, LEZ). Trends in NO_x, NO₂ and particulate matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}) for 2005–2016 in background and roadside locations; and trends in traffic increments were calculated in both cities to address their impact.

- **Asif et al. (2019)**

According to the researchers, it is necessary to trade off environmental impact and mining performance, preferably using an integrated life cycle modeling approach, while quantifying the air emissions.

- **Ba et al. (2019)**

According to researchers, the consequences of indoor and outdoor air pollution on human health are of great concern nowadays. In this study, researchers firstly evaluated indoor and outdoor air pollution levels (CO, CO₂, NO, NO₂, PM₁₀) at an urban site in Dakar city center and at a rural site.

- **Krishan et al. (2019)**

According to researchers, nowadays, monitoring and prediction of air quality parameters are becoming significantly important research topics in the context of increasing urbanization and industrialization.

- **Perugu (2019)**

Based on the results analysis and background information from other studies, the researcher found that the faster degradation of local vehicles are due to different local operating conditions like worse traffic congestion/slower vehicle speeds and local road conditions.

- **Gogikar et al. (2019)**

According to researchers, the particulate matter (PM) concentration forecast is an important component to evaluate the air quality over any region of the world. The results are vital when it comes to health concern issues related to air pollution in developing countries like India.

- **Tsai et al. (2018)**

According to researchers, with the advance of technology, it is increasingly exhaust emissions have caused air pollution. In particular, PM_{2.5} (Particulate Matter) has been proven that it has a great correlation with human health. Therefore, the detection and prediction of PM 2.5 air pollution is an important issue.

- **Yusri et al. (2018)**

Researchers report that alternative fuel is one of the widely used fuel substitutions for both petrol and diesel in the field of internal combustion engine.

- **Ahlers and Shen (2018)**

Researchers report that heavy smog suffocating China's cities is increasingly being perceived as a threat by both the population and the authorities.

- **Dominguez-Saez et al. (2018)**

The objective of this study is the development and evaluation of two models to predict instantaneous exhaust emissions of CO₂, NO_x, and particle number concentration and geometric mean diameter in accumulation mode (30–560 nm) and in nucleation mode (5.6–30 nm) of a 2.0 euro 4 diesel engine fueled with pure diesel and animal fat in different proportions.

- **Bhowmik et al. (2018)**

This study evaluates the effects of diesel fuel adulteration on the performance and exhaust emission characteristics of an existing diesel engine. Kerosene is added to diesel fuel in volumetric proportions of 5, 10, 15, and 20%. Adulterated fuel significantly reduced the oxides of nitrogen emissions of the engine.

- **Oudin et al. (2018)**

The aim of this study was to assess the longitudinal association between exposures of fine ambient particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) from residential wood burning, and vehicle exhaust, with dementia.

- **Bronnum-Hansen et al. (2018)**

The purpose of this study was to estimate the health benefits of reduced exposure to vehicle emissions assessed as NO₂ at the residence among the citizens of Copenhagen Municipality, Denmark.

- **Cecchel et al. (2018)**

This study presents a modeling system to evaluate the impact of weight reduction in light commercial vehicles with diesel engines on air quality and greenhouse gas emissions.

- **Mehra et al. (2018)**

According to researchers, in today's era, the computational capabilities of artificial neural network have endorsed to be bedrock and inferences in many fields, including internal-combustion engines.

- **Paul et. al (2018)**

The present study surveys the effects on performance and emission parameters of a partially modified single cylinder direct injection diesel engine fueled with diesohol blends under varying compressed natural gas flow rates in dual fuel mode.

- **Saree et al. (2017)**

According to researchers, reduction of exhaust emission and fuel consumption is one of the most important challenges in the engine communities..

- **Chang and Tseng (2017)**

According to researchers, the first target of this study is to investigate the correlation of factory air pollution source data and stock farming data nearby air monitoring stations to the annual mean PM_{2.5} concentration of nearby air monitoring stations.

- **Zimmer and Koch (2017)**

This paper estimates the potential of fuel tax reforms to curb harmful air pollutants and carbon emissions from road transport in Europe.

- **He et al. (2017)**

This study analyzed the air pollution characteristics and their relation to multi-scale meteorological conditions during 2014–2015 in 31 provincial capital cities in China.

- **Dharma et al. (2017)**

The objective of this study is to investigate the performance and exhaust emissions of a single-cylinder direct injection diesel engine fueled with *Jatropha curcas*-*Ceiba pentandra* biodiesel-diesel blends.

- **Xu et al. (2017)**

This paper focused on the analysis of vehicle emission based on the Hefei remote sensing data during the last three years.

- **Catalano and Galatioto (2017)**

This research proposes a novel approach to improve the ability to forecast low frequency extreme events of transport-related pollution in urban areas using a limited input data set. The approach is based on the idea of a self-managing model, able to adapt to unexpected changes in pollution level. In more detail, for a given combination of variables, it selects the most suitable prediction model within a set of alternative air quality models, estimated for a wider range of locations and conditions.

- **Kumar et al. (2017)**

The present study focused on seasonal relations and predictions of the ozone (O₃) coupled with NO₂ and meteorology.

- **Jaikumar et al. (2017)**

This paper presents the characterization and modeling of exhaust emissions released from the passenger cars on urban roads under heterogeneous traffic conditions.

- **Saxena and Mathur (2017)**

Researchers report that recent years concerns related with ambient air quality is prominent due to increments in the entropy and ozone layer depletion.

- **Anake et al. (2016)**

According to researchers, ambient atmospheric fine particle emission contribution to industrial pollution load is hard to quantify due to absence of air quality monitoring stations and difficulties in assessing suitable analytical instruments.

- **Gennaro et al. (2016)**

According to researchers, over the last 50 years, global earth's temperature has markedly risen likely because of growing emission of anthropogenic greenhouse gas concentrations.

- **Font and Fuller (2016)**

According to researchers, a large number of policy initiatives are being taken at the European level, across the United Kingdom and in London to improve air quality and reduce population exposure to harmful pollutants from traffic emissions.

- **Chiwewe and Ditsela (2016)**

In this paper, models are created to predict the levels of ground level Ozone at particular locations based on the cross-correlation and spatial-correlation of different air pollutants whose readings are obtained from several different air quality monitoring stations in Gauteng province, South Africa, including the City of Johannesburg which is on the cusp of being one of the world's megacities and is currently the most polluted city in the country.

- **Anake et al. (2016)**

According to researchers, atmospheric aerosols pose a serious threat to environmental quality and health of the public. Several studies in Nigeria have documented the pollution levels from coarse particles but very few have elucidated the nature of the fine particles in the context of air quality index.

- **Zhu et al. (2016)**

According to researchers, vehicle emissions are greatly influenced by various factors that are related to engine technology and driving conditions.

- **Matthias et al. (2016)**

According to researchers, scenarios for future shipping emissions in the North Sea have been developed in the framework of the Clean North Sea Shipping project.

- **Chakraborty et al. (2016)**

The present study tries to harness the synergistic exploits of diesel-LPG dual fuel platform coupled with artificial neural network for addressing the environmental intimidation due to pollution, rigorous emission legislatives and the future energy insecurity.

- **Sekar et al. (2016)**

The present study attempts to predict hourly ozone (O₃) and oxides of nitrogen (NO_x) concentrations near a traffic intersection in megacity Delhi, India, using artificial neural network (ANN) with the Levenberg–Maquardt (LM) algorithm and decision tree algorithms.

- **Sekar et al. (2016)**

According to researchers, air pollution in megacities have caught attention of both researchers and policymakers because of increasing emissions, poor air quality, and potential adverse health impacts on densely inhabited populations.

- **Mishra and Goyal (2016)**

The main objective of the present study is to develop the model that can forecast daily concentrations of air pollutions in one-day advance.

- **Patra et al. (2016)**

According to researchers, Particulate matter (PM) is a major pollutant in and around opencast mine areas. The problem of degradation of air quality due to opencast mine is more severe than those in underground mine.

- **Alves et al. (2015)**

The present investigation illustrates the emissions of eight in-use gasoline and diesel passenger cars using the official European driving cycle and the ARTEMIS real-world driving cycles.

- **Mishra and Goyal (2015)**

The statistical regression and specific computational intelligence based models are presented in this paper for the forecasting of hourly NO₂ concentrations at a historical monument Taj Mahal, Agra.

- **Zhang et al. (2015)**

According to researchers, PM_{2.5} pollution has become of increasing public concern because of its relative importance and sensitivity to population health risks. Accurate predictions of PM_{2.5} pollution and population exposure risks are crucial to developing effective air pollution control strategies.

- **Reichle et al. (2015)**

In this paper, we present results of an extensive review and analysis of available exhaust speciation data for total organic gases (TOG) for spark ignition (SI) engines running on gasoline/ethanol blends now in widespread use, and compression ignition (CI) engines running on diesel fuel. Researchers identified two data sets best suited for development of exhaust speciation profiles.

- **Faber et al. (2015)**

According to researchers, aerosol emissions from construction sites have a strong impact on local air quality.

- **Ganesan et al. (2015)**

According to researchers, the growing demand of DG (diesel electric generators) has led to air pollution and green house gas emissions, especially CO₂ (Carbon-di-oxide).

- **Pedata et al. (2015)**

According to researchers, there is an urgent need to develop i) reliable methods to measure sub-10 nm particles at the exhaust and in the atmosphere and ii) a robust correlation between the chemical structure of the molecules making up combustion-generated nanoparticles and health burden of new combustion technologies.

- **Brugge et al. (2015)**

The literature consistently shows associations of adverse cardiovascular and pulmonary outcomes with residential proximity to highways and major roadways. Community-level tactics for reducing exposure include the following: 1) high-efficiency particulate arrestance (HEPA) filtration; 2) appropriate air-intake locations; 3) sound proofing, insulation; 4) land-use buffers; 5) vegetation or wall barriers; 6) street-side trees, hedges and vegetation; 7) decking over highways; 8) urban design including placement of buildings; 9) garden and park locations; and 10) active-travel locations, including bicycling and walking paths.

- **Mohammadhassani et al. (2015)**

In this study, the combination of artificial neural network (ANN) and ant colony optimization (ACO) algorithm has been utilized for modeling and reducing NO_x and soot emissions from a direct injection diesel engine.

- **Ganesan et al. (2015)**

The researchers developed an artificial neural network model, with the help of which Performance and exhaust emissions of diesel generator were predicted. The application of the newly developed model showed better results.

- **Elangasinghe et al. (2014)**

In this paper, researchers propose a methodology for extracting the key information from routinely-available meteorological parameters and the emission pattern of sources present throughout the year (e.g. traffic emissions) to build a reliable and physically-based ANN air pollution forecasting tool.

- **Benjamin et al. (2014)**

According to researchers, over the last few years, the use of artificial neural networks (ANNs) has increased in many areas of engineering. Artificial neural network have been applied to many environmental engineering problems and have demonstrated some degree of success. The aim of study is to develop neural network air quality prediction model for the sensitive area of Ujjain city (Mahakal Mandir) in India.

- **Azid et al. (2014)**

This study focused on the pattern recognition of Malaysian air quality based on the data obtained from the Malaysian Department of Environment..

- **Taghavifar et al. (2014)**

According to researchers, broad information on exhaust emissions facilitates the design of modern machinery and processing equipment with modified quality specifications. This paper is aimed at investigating soot and NO_x emissions as affected by crank-angle, liquid mass evaporated, mean diesel mass fraction and heat release rate of group-hole injectors utilizing computational fluid dynamics while the objective parameters are prognosticated by a supervised artificial neural network.

- **Font et al. (2014)**

According to researchers, road widening schemes in urban areas are often proposed as a solution to traffic congestion and as a means of stimulating economic growth.

- **AhmadIsiyaka et al. (2014)**

This study aims to investigate the spatial variation in the source of air pollution; identify the most significant parameters contributing to the air pollution and to develop the best receptor model for predicting air pollution index.

- **Lähde et al. (2014)**

Researchers report that a two weeks measurement campaign by a mobile laboratory van was performed at downtown Helsinki, Finland, in winter 2010.

- **Roy et al. (2014)**

The present study explores the potential of artificial neural network to predict the performance and exhaust emissions of an existing single cylinder four-stroke CRDI engine under varying EGR strategies.

- **Zielinska et al. (2014)**

The purpose of this study was to provide a better understanding of the potential contributions of emissions from gas production operations to population exposure to air toxics in the Barnett Shale region.

- **Shrivastav and Sharma (2014)**

The aim of this study was modeling of ambient air pollutants through ANN, in industrial area of Ujjain city in India and the study was carried out on modeling of air pollutants like SO_x, NO_x, SPM and RSPM using Artificial Neural Network.

- **Yadav et al. (2014)**

The aim of this study was modeling of ambient air pollutants through ANN in industrial area of Ujjain city in India and the study was carried out on modeling of air pollutants like SPM and RSPM using Artificial Neural Network.

- **Chan and Jian (2013)**

According to researchers, an artificial neural network (ANN) is a commonly used approach to estimate or forecast air pollution levels, which are usually assessed by the concentrations of air contaminants such as nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide, carbon monoxide, ozone, and suspended particulate matters (PMs) in the atmosphere of the concerned areas.

- **Mutalib et al. (2013)**

The objective of this study is to identify spatial and temporal patterns in the air quality at three selected Malaysian air monitoring stations based on an eleven-year database (January 2000–December 2010).

- **Cay et al. (2013)**

This study investigates the use of ANN modeling to predict BSFC (break specific fuel consumption), exhaust emissions that are CO (carbon monoxide) and HC (unburned hydrocarbon), and AFR (*air-fuel ratio*) of a spark ignition engine which operates with methanol and gasoline.

- **Jafarmadar and Taghavifar (2013)**

According to researchers, artificial neural network was considered in previous studies for prediction of engine performance and emissions.

- **Pedata et al. (2013)**

According to researchers, epidemiological studies indicate that air pollution, considered one of the major public health concerns in industrialized cities, not only have respiratory effects but also increase cardiovascular morbidity and mortality.

- **Azid et al. (2013)**

This paper describes the application of principal component analysis and artificial neural network to predict the air pollutant index within the seven selected Malaysian air monitoring stations in the southern region of Peninsular Malaysia based on seven years database (2005-2011).

- **Olamijulo and Ana (2013)**

The aim of this study is to determine the concentration of traffic related air pollutants at major and busy road intersections in two Local Government Areas of Ibadan, Nigeria.

- **Huang et al. (2012)**

In this study, a new method was proposed to systematically identify the local PM₁₀ emission sources for priority regulation in urban air quality management through a coupled MM5-CAMx-PSAT modeling system.

- **Laumbach et al. (2012)**

According to researchers, mounting evidence suggests that air pollution contributes to the large global burden of respiratory and allergic diseases, including asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, pneumonia, and possibly tuberculosis.

- **Sgro et al. (2012)**

According to researchers, while nuclei particles are found in vehicle emissions in low mass concentration, they are being studied since their number concentration may be high and they may contribute to the surface composition of larger particles and health effects associated with pollution.

- **Commodo et al. (2012)**

In this work we investigate the size distribution of particulate matter emitted from a heating stove burning pellet.

- **Gasana et al. (2012)**

Researchers report that asthma affects more than 17 million people in the United States; 1/3 of these are children. Children are particularly vulnerable to airborne pollution because of their narrower airways and because they generally breathe more air per pound of body weight than adults, increasing their exposure to air pollutants. However, the results from previous studies on the association between motor vehicle emissions and the development of childhood wheeze and asthma are conflicting. The researchers conducted a meta-analysis to clarify their potential relationship.

- **Cay et al. (2012)**

This study deals with artificial neural network (ANN) modeling to predict the brake specific fuel consumption, effective power and average effective pressure and exhaust gas temperature of the methanol engine.

- **Hung et al. (2012)**

During the research work, the relationship between breast cancer mortality and air pollution was examined using an ecological design.

- **Traviss (2012)**

This article summarizes the known impacts of biodiesel on air quality and health effects, comparing emissions and exposure research.

- **Sgro et al. (2012)**

This work describes the use of well-controlled laboratory flames to produce aerosols of organic carbon (OC) as model particles representative of the OC fraction of combustion-generated particulate matter emissions in fresh exhausts.

- **Nagendra & Khare (2006)**

This paper describes a step-by-step procedure to model the nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) dispersion phenomena using the ANN technique.

3. Gaps in the Research and Objectives of Proposed Research

Following points represent the gaps investigated during the survey of available literature:

a) There is very limited number of research papers available which focus on the research on the investigations on air quality due to exhaust emissions

The research gap lies in the limited number of studies specifically focused on investigating the impact of exhaust emissions on air quality. While there is extensive literature on air pollution and emissions in general, few studies have comprehensively explored the direct relationship between exhaust emissions from vehicles or industrial sources and their specific contributions to air quality degradation. This gap highlights the need for more targeted research to understand the mechanisms, extent, and regional variations of exhaust-related air pollution, as well as its effects on human health and the environment. Addressing this gap is crucial for developing effective emissions control policies and improving air quality management.

b) There is also a very limited research papers available which has focuses on the investigations on air quality of different cities of India

The research gap stems from the limited availability of studies focusing on the investigation of air quality across different cities in India. While air pollution is a well-documented issue in the country, most existing research is either concentrated on a few major metropolitan areas or generalized at the national level, leaving many cities underexplored in terms of their unique air quality challenges. This gap restricts a comprehensive understanding of the varying sources and impacts of air pollution across diverse urban environments in India. Filling this gap is essential for region-specific strategies to effectively manage and improve air quality across the country.

Following points represent the objectives of the research work:

a) To select justified number of air quality monitoring stations at different locations in the targeted city

The research objective is to develop a systematic approach for selecting a justified number of air quality monitoring stations at various locations within a targeted city, specifically for exhaust

emission analysis. This involves identifying optimal monitoring sites based on factors such as traffic patterns, industrial emissions, population density, meteorological conditions, and proximity to pollution sources. The goal is to ensure that the placement and number of stations provide a comprehensive and representative dataset that accurately reflects the city's air quality, enabling more precise analysis of exhaust emissions. Achieving this objective is crucial for developing effective air quality management strategies and for better understanding the spatial distribution and impact of exhaust emissions on urban air quality.

b) To monitor the different concentrations present in the ambient air at all the monitoring stations

The research objective is to monitor the various pollutant concentrations present in the ambient air at all selected air quality monitoring stations in the targeted city, with a focus on exhaust emissions. This involves measuring key pollutants such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), particulate matter (PM), and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) emitted from vehicles and industrial sources. By continuously collecting data from multiple monitoring locations, the study aims to provide a detailed assessment of how these pollutants vary across different areas, times, and environmental conditions. This objective is essential for understanding the spatial and temporal distribution of exhaust emissions and their impact on urban air quality, informing mitigation efforts, and shaping effective pollution control policies.

c) To perform ambient air quality monitoring in all the monitoring stations, at regular intervals, for evaluating the Air Quality Index (AQI)

The research objective is to conduct ambient air quality monitoring at regular intervals across all selected monitoring stations to evaluate the Air Quality Index (AQI), specifically in relation to exhaust emissions. This involves systematically measuring pollutants like carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), particulate matter (PM), and ozone (O₃), which are primarily emitted from vehicles and industrial activities. Regular monitoring ensures that pollutant levels are tracked consistently over time, allowing for accurate assessment of air quality variations. The resulting AQI values provide a standardized way to communicate air pollution levels and their potential health impacts, guiding policy decisions and public awareness on the severity of air pollution caused by exhaust emissions in the targeted city.

d) Development of an ambient air quality model using artificial neural network (ANN) approach

The research objective is to develop an ambient air quality model using an artificial neural network (ANN) approach, with a focus on exhaust emissions. This involves leveraging the predictive capabilities of ANN to model complex relationships between exhaust emissions and air pollutant concentrations. By training the neural network on historical data from monitoring stations—such as traffic density, meteorological conditions, and pollutant levels—the model can accurately predict future air quality trends and identify pollution hotspots. This approach offers a more dynamic and adaptive method for assessing the impact of exhaust emissions on ambient air quality compared to traditional models. The developed ANN model can provide real-time air quality forecasting, aiding in more effective air pollution management and decision-making processes.

4. Conclusion

This research paper recognizes the various academic aspects involved in studying exhaust emissions and air quality assessment. It highlights the importance of addressing current environmental challenges and aims to offer valuable insights and direction to researchers, scientists, and engineers working in this area. By doing so, the paper aspires to contribute to advancements in environmental protection, helping to improve air quality and promote sustainable practices in emissions control and pollution management. This guidance could serve as a foundation for future research and innovation, ultimately enhancing environmental well-being.

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